

GERMPLASM IMPROVEMENT

Genetics

Inheritance of hybrid weakness in indica/japonica rice crosses

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We investigated the inheritance of hybrid weakness occurring in F₂, F₃, and subsequent generations in remote crosses of rice.

The F₁ plants of indica (IR24, CR44, Milyang 23, and Suweon 258) and japonica varieties from Japan showed vigorous growth and partial sterility.

The weak segregants in F₂ were slightly yellow at the seedling stage. Fresh weight of their aboveground phytomass 60 d after transplanting averaged about one-tenth as much as that of normal plants. Some of them died before heading. Mature plants were stunted and had only a few short panicles. Numbers of normal and weak plants observed in six F₂ populations are given in Table 1. The relative frequency of weak segregants was 2.2 to 7.5%, which fit the expected frequency of 6.3% under a duplicate recessive gene system.

In the F₃ lines derived from randomly sampled F₂ plants of Toyonishiki/Milyang 23, 27 lines produced all normal plants, 11 lines segregated 15 normal to 1 weak, 14 lines segregated 3 normal to 1 weak, and 2 lines produced all weak plants. This segregation pattern gave a good fit to the expected 7:4:41 (c² = 1.5238, 0.60 < P < 0.70).

The BC₁F₁ plants were all normal. The segregation of BC₁F₂ lines gave a good fit to the expected 2 (all normal):1 (segregating 15:1) : 1 (segregating 3:1) ratio in all crosses (Table 2).

A duplicate recessive gene system in which double recessive homozygotes express weakness can be adapted to these segregation patterns. This is a new

Table 1. Segregation for hybrid weakness in F₂ populations.

Cross combination	Plants (no.)			Weak plants (%)	χ^2 (15:1)	P (df=1)
	Normal	Weak	Total			
Reimei/IR24	128	4	132	3.03	2.3354	0.10-0.20
CR44/Reimei	319	26	345	7.54	0.9741	0.30-0.40
Akihikari/Milyang 23	131	3	134	2.22	3.6796	0.05-0.10
Toyonishiki/Milyang 23	132	8	140	5.71	0.0686	0.75-0.80
Milyang 23/IG-15 ^a	631	35	666	5.26	1.1247	0.25-0.30
Reimei/Suweon 258	129	3	132	2.27	3.5636	0.05-0.10

^a IG-15 = Ishiokamochi 15.

Table 2. Segregation for hybrid weakness in BC₁F₁ populations and BC₁F₂ lines.

Cross combination ^a	Plants in BC ₁ F ₁ populations (no.)		BC ₁ F ₂ lines (no.) with the ratio (normal:weak)			χ^2 (2:1:1)	P (df=2)
	Normal	Weak	1:0	15:1	3:1		
Reimei/M23/M23	28	0	16	7	5	0.8571	0.60-0.70
Reimei/M23/Reimei	92	0	53	19	20	2.1522	0.30-0.40
M23/Akihikari/M23	18	0	8	6	4	0.6667	0.70-0.75
M23/Toyonishiki/M23	48	0	25	10	13	0.4583	0.75-0.80
S258/Reimei/S258	34	0	21	6	7	1.9412	0.30-0.40
Reimei/S258/Reimei	40	0	22	9	9	0.4000	0.80-0.90
Reimei/IR24/IR24	20	0	13	4	3	1.9000	0.30-0.40
Reimei/IR24/Reimei	34	0	17	10	7	0.5294	0.75-0.80
CR44/Reimei/CR44	46	0	22	15	9	1.6522	0.40-0.50

^a M23 = Milyang 23, S258 = Suweon 258.

genic system for hybrid weakness in remote crosses of rice. Hybrid breakdown in F₂ and later inbred generations due to hybrid weakness and partial sterility

would eliminate desirable recombinants and distort segregations of genes in breeding programs using indica-japonica hybridization. □

Breeding methods

Inheritance of a low-tillering plant type in rice

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A major gene controlling the low tillering trait was found in Japanese variety

Aikawa 1. This spontaneous mutant was discovered by a Japanese farmer in 1980. Restricted tillering, long and thick culms, and dense panicles are the mutant-type characters that distinguish the variety's plant type.

We investigated the inheritance mode of the plant type using a cross between Aikawa 1 and Chiyonishiki, which is

Table 1. Characteristics of plant type components of Aikawa 1, Chiyonishiki, and their F₁.^a

Variety	Days to heading (no.)	Culm length (cm)	Panicles per plant (no.)	Diameter of main culm ^b (mm)	Panicle characters					Weight of a brown rice grain (mg)
					Panicle length (cm)	Spikelets (no.)	Seed fertility (%)	Primary branches (no.)	Secondary branches (no.)	
Aikawa 1	98.0	93.6	4.9	10.00	21.7	221.4	87.4	16.3	45.4	23.3
Chiyonishiki	103.0	76.5	11.8	5.37	18.3	97.1	96.9	9.5	16.3	22.4
F ₁	96.0 (96)	91.4 (108)	8.4 (101)	7.92 (103)	20.7 (104)	182.6 (115)	91.0 (99)	14.0 (109)	36.8 (119)	23.1 (101)

^a Figures in parentheses are percentages of F₁ compared with the midparent. ^b Measured at the central part of the fifth internode.